

Use of Laboratory Facilities as a Predictor of Students' Biology Achievement in Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State

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Abstract

This study employed a quasi-experimental design to investigate the availability and use of laboratory facilities as predictors of students' biology achievement in the Ukwuani Local Government Area (LGA) of Delta State, Nigeria. For the purpose of this study, a representative sample was created by randomly selecting seven public secondary schools in the area. From each of these schools, ten S.S. 2 students were randomly chosen, with equal numbers drawn from the schools with the highest and lowest records of biology laboratory facility availability and usage. The Biology Laboratory Facility Checklist (BLFC) and the Biology Achievement Test (BAT) were employed as the research instruments for the study. The BAT demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.78 using the Kuder-Richardson 21 (KR-21) method, while the BLFC was reviewed by two Biology experts from the Delta State Teaching Service. Two research questions and a null hypothesis guided the study's conduct. The hypothesis was tested at a 5% alpha significance level using a t-test for independence to determine the differences in students' Biology achievement between schools with the highest and lowest levels of Biology Laboratory Facilities, as determined by the BLFC. The study revealed a poor level of biology laboratory facilities in the public secondary schools in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State and found that no significant difference exists in the Biology achievement of public school students between schools, with the highest and lowest levels of Biology Laboratory Facilities in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State. Among other measures, the Delta State Ministry of Education was recommended to provide intervention for laboratory facilities in schools such as Obinomba Mixed Secondary School, which demonstrated a pitiable level of functional biology laboratory facilities.

Keywords: *Biology laboratory, Secondary education, Science education, Student achievement.*

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Introduction

In the pursuit of scientific knowledge, laboratory activities play a crucial role in developing students' critical thinking skills, dexterity, and other abilities related to scientific processes. Consequently, one cannot successfully discuss a well-rounded scientific education without engaging in laboratory practices. This aligns with the goals of science education, which aims to cultivate in the Nigerian students a passion for inquiry necessary for developing a rational mindset. Accordingly, Biology, being a science subject in Nigerian secondary schools, utilises laboratory experiences to provide meaningful science education for students taking the subject (FME, 2009).

Biology is a broad subject that encompasses various aspects of living organisms, including their composition, function, and the interactions between the living world and the non-living world (Waddington, 2017). Through its scientific methodology, biology empowers learners to engage in critical and analytical thinking while embodying the essence of inquiry. Consequently, biology education is vital to scientific exploration, as it equips students with a profound understanding of the intricate dynamics of life on Earth (Ahmad et al., 2018). Therefore, the importance of biology as a field in the economic, industrial, and social aspects of society and humanity cannot be emphasised enough and should be acknowledged at every level.

Teachers usually integrate laboratory practical sessions with traditional classroom discussions to effectively engage students in biology. Thus, it is reasonable to expect a link between the availability and usage of biology laboratory facilities and the rate of academic achievement among students in secondary school Biology.

Uhumuavbi and Okodugha (2014) highlighted that using laboratories for teaching science helps students develop practical skills, which may result in better retention of information and more positive attitudes toward school subjects. However, recent data from the WAEC Chief Examiners Report on Practical Biology revealed a poor level of students' achievement in Nigeria. Consider Table 1 below.

Table 1. Chief Examiner's Report on Students' Performance in WAEC Biology Practical Examination

Year	Raw mean score	Standard deviation
2019	31	11.18
2020	42	12.21
2021	31	11.83
2022	36	11.66

Many factors may influence student achievement in these examinations, as noted in Table 1 above (Ihejamaizu & Ochui, 2016). This study specifically aims to assess:

- (i.) The availability and establishment of Biology laboratory facilities in public secondary schools in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State
- (ii.) Whether a significant difference exists in students' Biology achievements between schools with the highest and lowest levels of Biology Laboratory facilities in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State.

This is essential because practical proficiency is also required for students who wish to pursue further careers in biology-related disciplines, such as Medicine and Surgery, Pharmacy, Microbiology, and Nursing. These laboratory instructional experiences would engage students in activities that promote essential thinking skills such as observing, inferring, classifying, measuring, and interpreting data. As a result, learning becomes more engaging and interesting. Conversely, lacking these materials could negatively affect students' interest, enrollment, and overall achievement. Effective practical experience in science thus depends significantly on the kind of laboratory apparatus and equipment available. This implies that one cannot expect a smooth, practical instructional experience for students without negotiating for the appropriate apparatus and equipment required to create such experiences (Ughamadu, 2016; Oyovwi & Iroriteraye-Adjekpovu, 2021)

Iroriteraye-Adjekpovu (2022) revealed a significant difference in academic performance between schools with adequate laboratory facilities and those with inadequate biology practicals in the Ethiope East Local Government Area of Delta State. Similarly, Katcha and Wushishi (2015)

observed a significant difference in the academic achievement of biology students exposed to adequately equipped laboratories and those exposed to inadequately equipped laboratories, with the difference favouring those exposed to adequately equipped laboratories in Abuja, Nigeria. Furthermore, Geleta (2016) found that insufficient science laboratory equipment led to low academic achievement among students of Biology, Chemistry, and Physics in the high schools of the Ilu Abba Bora Zone in Southwestern Ethiopia. Abdulrasaq (2018) also rightly observed that science teachers cannot function effectively without the necessary materials for practical activities.

A well-managed laboratory instructional process fosters better retention, critical thinking, and process skills in science students (Iroriteraye-Adjekpovu, 2021). Hence, these significant research works underscore the dangers of neglecting practical activities in science classroom interactions, as this may severely undermine not only students' understanding of concepts but also their overall achievement in the subject area, starkly contrasting with what effective science education should embody.

As the field of science continues to evolve, science education must progress in a manner that equips students with the skills necessary to address the challenges of the future (Egboduku & Iroriteraye-Adjekpovu, 2025). Based on this, the 21st-century science education has witnessed different dimensions of the laboratory, placing a strong emphasis on the seamless integration of cutting-edge technology. The advent of virtual and remote laboratories has revolutionised experimental procedures, making them not only more resourceful and precise but also widely accessible to a broader audience. These technological advancements significantly enhance the reach of science education, allowing students to engage in hands-on learning experiences within a safe and controlled environment. This shift not only fosters a deeper understanding of scientific concepts but also encourages curiosity and innovation among learners.

This study aims to determine how the availability and use of biology laboratory facilities might predict students' achievement outcomes in public secondary schools within the Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State.

Research Questions

The research questions guiding this study are as follows:

- i. To what extent are Biology laboratory facilities available in the public secondary schools in the Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?
- ii. To what extent does a significant difference exist in students' Biology achievement between the schools with the highest and lowest levels of Biology laboratory facilities in the Ukwuani LGA of Delta State?

Research Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference in students' Biology achievement between the schools with the highest and lowest levels of Biology Laboratory Facilities, in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State.

Research Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental design to investigate the availability and use of laboratory facilities as predictors of students' achievement in Biology within the Ukwuani Local Government Area (LGA) of Delta State, Nigeria. Seven public secondary schools in the area were randomly chosen for the research. Two research questions and a null hypothesis guided the study's conduct.

The research instruments used were the Biology Laboratory Facility Checklist (BLFC) and the Biology Achievement Test (BAT). The BAT demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.78 using the

Kuder-Richardson 21 (KR-21) method, while the BLFC was reviewed by two Biology experts from the Delta State Teaching Service. The BLFC consists of 50 items on a four-point Likert scale, which effectively measures the availability, functionality, and frequency of use of specific biology laboratory facilities in schools. Similarly, the BAT includes 25 biology test questions focused on Cell Biology, aligning with the approved scheme of work for students in Delta State schools.

The researcher visited all selected schools to ensure the accuracy of the data collected through the BLFC. After analysing the data, the researcher identified the schools with both the highest and lowest levels of biology laboratory facilities. From each of these schools, a representative sample of ten S.S. 2 Biology students was randomly selected, comprising ten students from the school with the highest record of facility availability and usage, as well as ten students from the school with the lowest record. The BAT was then administered to both groups of students, and the obtained data were analysed using descriptive statistics. To examine the hypothesis, an independent t-test was conducted at a 5% alpha significance level to decide the differences in Biology achievement between the two student groups.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: To what extent are Biology laboratory facilities available in the public secondary schools in the Ukwuani Local Government Area of Delta State?

Table 2. Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Measure of Availability, Functionality, and Use of Biology Laboratory Facilities within the Representative Samples in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State (N=7)

S/N	Name of school	% of available, functional and utilised facilities	% of available, fairly functional and fairly utilised facilities	% of available but not functional facilities	% of not-available facilities.
1.	Amai Secondary Commercial School, Amai.	45%	19%	-	36%
2.	Obiaruku Grammar School, Obiaruku.	68%	10%	-	22%
3.	Umutu Mixed Secondary School, Umutu.	40%	12%	-	48%
4.	Obinomba Mixed Secondary School, Obinomba.	15%	13%	-	72%
5.	Umuaja Mixed Secondary School, Umuaja.	30%	30%	-	40%
6.	Boys Secondary School, Obiaruku.	40%	35%	-	25%
7.	Umukwata Secondary School, Umukwata.	20%	28%	-	52%
Total		258	147	-	295
% mean		36.86%	21%	-	42.14%

Table 2 presents data from BLFC that enable an assessment of the availability, functionality, and usability of the biology laboratory facilities in secondary schools within Ukwuani LGA of Delta State. The data indicate that only an average of 36.86% of the expected biology laboratory facilities were available, functional, and utilised across the seven schools sampled for this study.

Approximately 42.14% of the expected biology laboratory facilities were not available. Additionally, 21% of the existing biology laboratory facilities were found to be in poor condition, which limited their effectiveness for practical biology experiences. The data also indicated that Obiaruku Grammar School in Obiaruku had 68% of the expected biology laboratory facilities, making it the school with the highest level of availability and usage of Biology laboratory facilities. Conversely, Obinomba Mixed Secondary School in Obinomba had only about 15% of the expected facilities, placing it at the lowest end of the spectrum. Overall, these findings suggest that the availability and usability of functional biology laboratory facilities in public schools within Ukwuani LGA, Delta State, are very poor.

Research Question 2: To what extent does a significant difference exist in students' Biology achievement between the schools with the highest and lowest levels of Biology laboratory facilities in the Ukwuani LGA of Delta State?

H0: There is no significant difference in students' Biology achievement between the schools with the highest and lowest levels of Biology Laboratory Facilities, in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State.

Table 3. T-Test Analysis of Students' Academic Achievement in the BAT between the Respective Schools with the Highest and Lowest Levels of Biology Laboratory Facilities in the Ukwuani LGA of Delta State

Variables	N	MEAN	S.D	df	t-cal.	P-value	Remark
Obiaruku Grammar School, Obiaruku (the highest level of expected Biology laboratory facilities).	20	69.00	8.08	18	0.415	0.682	Null hypotheses Accepted
Obinomba Mixed Secondary School, Obinomba (lowest level of expected Biology lab Facilities).		67.20	11.10				

Note: *Significant at 5% alpha level.

From the Table 3, the calculated t value is 0.415, with the degree of freedom being 18. Using a t-distribution table or calculator, the P-value can be obtained as 0.682. Hence, P-value (0.682) is greater than α (0.05). Therefore, we fail to reject the hypothesis. This indicates that there is no significant difference in students' Biology achievement between schools with the highest and lowest levels of Biology Laboratory Facilities in Ukwuani LGA, Delta State. Thus, the availability and use of biology laboratory facilities does not predict students' academic achievement in Biology.

However, this finding contradicts Rimamsomte et al. (2021) and Akanbi et al. (2018), who reported a strong positive link between the availability and use of Biology laboratory facilities and students' academic performance Biology. The results also do not agree with Abdurasaq et al. (2017), who found that physics students exposed to laboratory use performed significantly better than those not exposed to it. However, this study suggests that while the availability and use of Biology laboratory facilities may be beneficial in promoting science education, they do not exert any statistically significant difference in the achievement of biology students in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State.

Findings

The study revealed that:

1. The Biology laboratories in public secondary schools in Ukwuani LGA, Delta State, are significantly under-equipped.
2. The school with the lowest level of biology laboratory facilities in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State, as at the time of this study, is Obinomba Mixed Secondary School, Obinomba.
3. Obiaruku Grammar School in Obiaruku tends to possess the highest level of available and functional biology laboratory facilities in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State.
4. The availability and use of Biology laboratory facilities do not exert any statistically significant difference in the academic achievement of biology students in the public schools in Ukwuani LGA of Delta State.

Conclusion

This study has indicated that, although Biology laboratory facilities are crucial for practical interactions in science education, it is important to note that their effectiveness also depends on other significant factors, such as learners' motivation and interest, teachers' characteristics, and learners' environment. Therefore, the availability and utilisation of Biology laboratory facilities alone cannot predict or guarantee improved students' academic achievement in secondary school Biology Education.

Recommendations

1. Delta State Ministry of Education should carry out an urgent assessment and inspection of the Biology laboratory facilities in secondary schools across Ukwuani Local Government Area. This will enable them to provide intervention support to schools like Obinomba Mixed Secondary School, whose Biology laboratory is in a poor state.
2. The Delta State Ministry of Education and other science-oriented organisations should fund more research to uncover the root cause of poor academic achievement in biology and other sciences generally. This will help promote the discovery of viable ways to improve students' engagement in the sciences.

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